

Ameliorative effects of *Enydra fluctuans* flavonoids against acephate toxicity in rat brain

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Abstract : Acephate, an organophosphorus pesticide, induces oxidative stress via free radical generation hampering tissues. Protective role of antioxidants present in *Enydra fluctuans* was evaluated against its toxicity. Male rats of Charles Foster strain treated orally with acephate (30 mg/kg bwt) and *Enydra fluctuans* extract (EFE) (20 mg of polyphenolic compounds expressed as gallic acid equivalents/kg bwt) for 14 days demonstrated a significant increase in SOD and non-enzymatic GSH, compared to normal and EFE gavaged groups, and decrease in catalase and GPx levels in brain of acephate treated group. An increased total cholesterol level was also noted. *In vitro* DPPH and ABTS^{+•} radical scavenging and reducing activities and lipid peroxidation, tested both in presence and absence of acephate, showed reduced activities in acephate treated tests. The present study gives an insight into the ill-effects of this organophosphate pesticide and the protective role of leafy vegetable polyphenols in minimizing those effects.

Keywords : Flavonoids, oxidative stress, lipid peroxidation, antioxidant enzymes, radical scavenging activity.

Introduction

Organophosphorus pesticides are a widely used, synthetic group of chemicals, applicable in agricultural and household purposes, the indiscriminate use of which, are seen to have detrimental effect on human health and non-target organisms^{1,2}. Accumulation of acetylcholine and consequential over-stimulation of AChE receptors is the chief mechanism of their action³. Besides, they have been proved to be associated with immunotoxicity, reproductive toxicity⁴, increase in lipid peroxidation and alteration in the status of the antioxidant enzymes in the body⁵ and recently hyperglycemia⁶. Moreover, their lipophilicity interferes with the normal functioning of the membranes by affecting the lipid bilayer⁷. Acephate (*O,S*-dimethyl acetylphosphoramidothioate) belonging to this group of pesticides causes oxidative stress via free radicals under normal conditions in the mitochondrial ETC and by enzymes such as lipoxygenases, peroxidases and dehydrogenases⁸. Further, it is S-oxidized to highly reactive metabolites within cells and tissues⁹ and gets readily converted to methamidophos acting as a potent carboxamidase inhibitor¹⁰.

Green leafy vegetables are rich sources of many nutrients and their beneficial role has partly been attributed to the antioxidant components present in them of which the major portion is formed by the flavonoids, isoflavones, lignans, catechins and isocatechins^{11,12}. The antioxidative role of these leafy vegetables has been well studied proving to have good radical scavenging activities and capability of inhibiting lipid peroxidation. Hence, an attempt had been made to determine the harmful side of this organophosphate on the basis of the *in vitro* assays, and the protective role of the antioxidative components present in the leafy vegetable, *Enydra fluctuans*, against the adverse effects of this pesticide, based on lipid peroxidation and antioxidant enzyme profiles *in vivo*.

Results and discussion

Total polyphenol and flavonoid content :

The total polyphenol content of the crude extract of *Enydra fluctuans* was 16.87 ± 0.001 mg/g GAE equivalents, using gallic acid as the standard and the total flavonoid content was measured as 10.62 ± 0.002 mg QE/g of dry leafy vegetable.

In vitro antioxidative assays :

A significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) in DPPH radical scavenging activity of the leafy vegetable was observed in the tests treated with acephate compared to the tests containing only the leafy vegetable extract. A higher EC_{50} value (1.63 ± 0.019) of $ABTS^{+\bullet}$ radical cation scavenging activity was observed in case of the acephate-treated tests compared to the non-treated group (1.07 ± 0.017). The reducing activity showed a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) at the low concentration. However, at higher concentrations of $2.5 \mu\text{g/ml}$ and $5 \mu\text{g/ml}$, there was a decrease in the activity of the leafy vegetable extract in the tests treated with acephate compared to the untreated test. A significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) in lipid peroxidation levels was observed in the acephate-treated tests when compared to the tests containing only the leafy vegetable extract. However, the leafy vegetable extract treated group showed much lower peroxidation values when compared to the control test containing only water (Fig. 1).

Enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidant activities :

Catalase activity was found to decrease significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the brain of the acephate-treated group, when compared to the normal group and the feeding of *E. fluctuans* extract had significantly restored the catalase activity. A significant increase ($p < 0.05$) was also noticed in the group treated with *E. fluctuans* extract alone. SOD showed increased activity in the acephate-treated group compared to the other three groups. Treatment with the leafy vegetable extract had definitely restored the SOD activity to near normal. Glutathione peroxidase (GPx) showed a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in activity in the acephate-treated group. However, treatment with the leafy vegetable extract had enhanced the activity of peroxidase in the acephate-treated group and the group treated with the leafy vegetable extract alone (Fig. 2). A significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in GSH was observed in the acephate-treated group when compared to the control group, which is also seen to increase significantly

Fig. 1. DPPH radical scavenging activity (a) and reducing power (b) of *E. fluctuans* (EFE) extract at 3 different concentrations of $1 \mu\text{g/ml}$, $2.5 \mu\text{g/ml}$ and $5 \mu\text{g/ml}$ and inhibition of lipid peroxidation by EFE (c) in the absence and presence of acephate. The values are expressed as Mean \pm SD, $n = 3$. Superscripts suggest a significant ($p < 0.05$) change in the value compared to the test without any pesticide treatment, i.e. the test containing only EFE at respective concentrations.

Fig. 2. Effect of *E. fluctuans* extract (EFE) on (a) catalase, (b) SOD and (c) GPx activity in 296 brain of acephate treated rats. ^aSignificantly different from control (Group I), the group treated with EFE alone (Group III) and EFE along with the pesticide treated group (Group IV), $p < 0.05$. ^bSignificantly different from Group II, $p < 0.05$.

($p < 0.05$) in case of the group treated with *E. fluctuans* extract (Fig. 3).

Total cholesterol :

The total cholesterol was found to increase significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the acephate-treated group compared to the control or the leafy vegetable extract-treated group. However, *E. fluctuans* extract did show a significant reduction in the cholesterol level against acephate induced increase in tissue cholesterol (Fig. 4).

A major threat in the area of pesticide toxicity has been posed by the organophosphate family of pesticides. They have well been recognized as initiators of tissue damage in the form of various cancers and other cellular apoptotic pathways^{13,14} and also as a major ROS generator that disrupts the normal antioxidative homeostasis^{2,15,16}. There is substantial evidence that oxidative stress plays an important role in the aging process¹⁷⁻²⁰ and age-related neurodegenerative diseases such as amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), Alzheimer's disease (AD), and

Parkinson's disease (PD). This theory has fostered the field of nutraceutical research, which investigates the effects of dietary antioxidants as a means to fight oxidative stress. Hence, a brief investigation of the antioxidative protection of a common leafy vegetable available locally against pesticide intoxication in the brain tissue *in vivo* as well *in vitro* was of much interest.

Leafy vegetables are a good storehouse of components called flavonoids²¹. Quercetin (3,3',4',5,7-pentahydroxyflavone), is a commonly and widely distributed flavonoid present in plants, mainly in the glycosidic forms such as rutin (5,7,3,4-OH, 3-rutinoside) which is antihyperglycaemic²². Among the various plant phenolics, rutin, quercetin, rutin hydrate and kaemferol have been identified in the methanolic extract of *Enydra fluctuans*, in a present study⁵. Since their basic mechanism of action is scavenging free radicals, these phenolic constituents might be held responsible for the present *in vitro* results.

SOD plays an important role in the dismutation of superoxide radicals to form hydrogen peroxide and mo-

Fig. 3. Effect of *E. fluctuans* extract on glutathione level in brain in acephate treated rats. ^aSignificantly different from control (Group I), the group treated with EFE alone (Group III) and EFE along with the pesticide treated group (Group IV), $p < 0.05$. ^bSignificantly different from the control (Group I), pesticide treated group (Group II) and the group treated with EFE and pesticide (Group IV), $p < 0.05$. ^cSignificantly different from the pesticide treated group (Group II) and the group treated with EFE alone (Group III), $p < 0.05$.

Fig. 4. Effect of the *E. fluctuans* extract on the total cholesterol level in brain in rats treated with acephate. ^aSignificantly different from control (Group I), the group treated with EFE alone (Group III) and EFE along with the pesticide treated group (Group IV), $p < 0.05$. ^bSignificantly different from the pesticide treated group (Group II) and the group treated with EFE along with the pesticide (Group IV), $p < 0.05$. ^cSignificantly different from the pesticide treated group (Group II) and EFE treated group (Group III), $p < 0.05$.

lecular oxygen, and acts as the first line of defense²³⁻²⁶. Catalase in turn converts peroxide to molecular oxygen and water thus nullifying the prooxidative effect of the free radicals^{27,28}. However, the presence of superoxide radicals inhibits the activity of catalase. In the present study, the elevation in SOD levels in brain may be attributed as a compensatory effect after acephate exposure, thus reducing the accumulation of superoxide anions in the tissue. CAT activity possibly decreases due to the

overproduction of hydrogen peroxide molecules. Binding of GSH *in vivo* to pesticides is a major pathway of their detoxification²⁹. However, prolonged exposure to pesticides causes a decrease in its ability to bind to them as they readily gets oxidized to GSSG in the process. In the present case, increase in the amounts may be justified as a protective measure towards brain cells. The GPx levels might have increased to maintain a steady flow of GSH molecules which can be made available to the foreign

particles inside the body. Cholesterol is a waxy, fat-like substance that the body needs to function normally. Reports suggest that plant extracts have the capacity to increase HDL (High Density Lipoprotein) levels in tissues and blood³⁰. HDL may hasten the removal of cholesterol from peripheral tissue to the liver for catabolism and excretion. Thus, the presence of *E. fluctuans* extract in our study might have protected the tissue from excessive cholesterol deposition in it, whereas the tissues display a high total cholesterol index in presence of the pesticide.

Experimental

Chemicals :

Methanol, hematoxylin, H₂O₂, ferric chloride, potassium ferricyanide were purchased from Sisco Research Laboratory (SRL), Mumbai, India; DPPH, ABTS⁺, TCA, GSH, GR, NADPH, DTNB from Sigma Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO); BSA standard from E. Merck India Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. Acephate (Technical grade-85% purity) was obtained from M/s Hindustan Insecticides Limited, Delhi, India.

Preparation of leafy vegetable extract :

Enydra fluctuans was collected from the local field and was authenticated by the Central National Herbarium, Shibpur, India vide the Letter No. CNH/120/2011/Tech II/607. Following the methods developed in the author's laboratory stem and leaves of *Enydra fluctuans* were washed thoroughly, oven-dried and ground to powder. It was then extracted using 80 : 20 methanol : water and concentrated in a rotary evaporator. The concentrates were pooled and the final concentrate was lyophilized to obtain the dry matter. The required amount for the dose (20 mg polyphenolic compounds expressed as gallic acid equivalents/kg body wt) was then dissolved in water to obtain the aqueous *E. fluctuans* extract (EFE). It was then frozen at -40 °C for further use in the animal experiment. For the *in vitro* tests, the methanolic extract was used directly without further concentration.

Preparation of pesticide solution :

The acephate solution was prepared by dissolving it in distilled water to obtain a clear solution. It was prepared on a daily basis so as to obtain the required dose of 30 mg/kg bwt for the *in vivo* assessment and 1 mg/ml for the *in vitro* experiment respectively.

Animal diet and treatment :

Male albino rats of Charles foster strain, weighing 100–130 g, were caged singly and provided with balanced diet and water *ad libitum*. The diets composed of fat-free casein, 18%; fat, 20% (sunflower oil); starch, 55%; salt-mixture 4% [composition of salt mixture No. 12 (in g) : NaCl 292.5; KH₂PO₄ 816.6; MgSO₄ 120.3; CaCO₃ 800.8; FeSO₄.7H₂O 56.6; KI 1.66; MnSO₄.2H₂O 9.35; ZnCl₂ 0.5452; CuSO₄.5H₂O 0.9988; CoCl₂.6H₂O 0.0476] cellulose 3%; one multivitamin capsule (vitamin A I.P. 10,000 units, thiamine mononitrate I.P. 5 mg, vitamin B I.P. 5 mg, calcium pantothenate USP 5 mg, niacinamide I.P. 50 mg, ascorbic acid I.P. 400 units, cholecalciferol USP 15 units, menadione I.P. 9.1 mg, folic acid I.P. 1 mg, vitamin E USP 0.1 mg) per kg of diet. The diets were adequate in all nutrients. They were maintained at 12 h light/dark conditions. The animal experiment was carried under the supervision of the Animal Ethical Committee of the Department of Chemical Technology, University of Calcutta.

The animals were divided into 4 groups comprising 8 rats (n = 8) in each group. Group I served as the control and was provided with normal diet. The animals in Group II were gavaged with the pesticide acephate only at a dose of 30 mg/kg body wt. Group III animals were administered by gavaging EFE at a dose of 20 mg/kg body wt. Group IV animals were given the pesticide, at a dose of 30 mg/kg body wt. along with EFE (20 mg/kg body wt.). The dose used for the pesticide was calculated as 1/100th of the LD₅₀, so that it showed no adverse effects or mortality in the animals.

All the treated rats were gavaged for 14 days and rats were sacrificed under mild anesthesia, blood was collected, and the tissues were immediately excised, blotted, and stored frozen (-40 °C) for further analysis.

Determination of total polyphenols and flavonoids :

Total polyphenol content of the leafy vegetable was determined by the Folin-ciocalteau method as described by Mattha³¹ using gallic acid as the standard. The total flavonoid content was determined according to the aluminum chloride colorimetric method described by Chang *et al.*³² using quercetin as the standard.

In vitro antioxidative assays :

DPPH stable radical scavenging activity :

In brief, different concentrations of samples were taken

in test tubes and volume adjusted to 1 ml by using distilled water. 5 ml of 0.1–0.2 mM methanolic solution of DPPH was added to the test tubes and shaken vigorously. The tubes were allowed to stand at room temperature for half an hour. Changes in the absorbance of the sample were measured at 517 nm. Radical scavenging activity was expressed as the inhibition percentage and calculated using the following formula³³. A similar set-up was also prepared where 1 mg/ml of acephate solution was also added along with the other reagents as described previously.

% Radical scavenging activity =

$$\frac{[(\text{Control OD} - \text{Sample OD}) / \text{Control OD}] \times 100}{\text{ABTS}^{+\bullet} \text{ radical cation scavenging activity}}$$

ABTS⁺ radical cation scavenging activity :

The activity was determined according to Re *et al.*³⁴. Briefly, 5 ml 7 mM ABTS was reacted with 88 μ L 140 mM potassium persulphate overnight in dark. Prior to use it was diluted with 50% ethanol for an initial absorbance of \approx 0.7 at 734 nm. 10 μ L of sample extract was added to 1 ml of diluted ABTS and the change in absorbance was recorded for 5 min at 1 s interval. The antioxidant capacity was expressed as EC₅₀, concentrations necessary for 50% reduction of ABTS. A similar set-up was also prepared where 1 mg/ml of acephate solution was also added along with the other reagents, as described previously.

Reducing activity :

Different concentrations of extracts were mixed with phosphate buffer (2.5 ml, 0.2 M, pH 6.6) and potassium ferricyanide (2.5 ml, 1%). The mixture was incubated at 50 °C for 20 min. 2.5 ml of 10% TCA was added to the mixture. 2.5 ml of this solution was mixed with distilled water (2.5 ml) and FeCl₃ (0.5 ml, 0.1%) and the absorbance measured at 700 nm. Increased absorbance of the reaction mixture indicates increased reducing power. All analysis was run in triplicates and averaged³⁵. A similar set-up was also prepared where 1 mg/ml of acephate solution was also added along with the other reagents as described previously.

Inhibition of lipid peroxidation in a linoleic acid emulsion :

It was determined by the method of Takao *et al.*³⁶. A reaction mixture containing 50 μ g/ml of extract, 2.3 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) and 2.5 ml of linoleic acid

emulsion was incubated in the dark at 37 °C. 0.1 ml of the mixture was added to 0.1 ml of 30% ammonium thiocyanate and 0.1 ml of ferrous chloride and mixed thoroughly. The absorbance was read at 500 nm after every 24 h. A similar set-up was also prepared where 1 mg/ml of acephate solution also was added along with the other reagents, as described previously.

Enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidant activities :

The tissues were first homogenized in phosphate buffer (50 mM potassium phosphate buffer at pH 7.0 for catalase and 1 M potassium phosphate buffer at pH 7.0 for SOD, GSH and GPx) and centrifuged. The supernatant was then used for measuring the following antioxidant enzymes. Catalase was measured according to the method of Aebi³⁷. CAT activity was measured spectrophotometrically and expressed as U/mg protein by the rate of decrease of hydrogen peroxide at 240 nm. SOD activity was assayed by measuring the auto oxidation of haematoxylin as described by Martin *et al.*³⁸. GSH was determined by the method of Ellman³⁹. Total activity of GPx (GPx EC.1.11.1.9.) was determined in the tissue homogenates and plasma according to Paglia and Valentine⁴⁰. The total protein was determined by the method of Lowry⁴¹. The total cholesterol was determined by the standard kit method.

Statistical analysis :

The data was expressed as Mean \pm SD. Differences among the experimental groups were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and the comparisons between the means were carried out using the Tukey test; $p < 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant in all the experiments.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can thus say that the extract of the leafy vegetable, *Enydra fluctuans*, prevents lipid peroxidation by inhibiting the production of free radicals and also by protecting the animals from deleterious effects of acephate by altering the antioxidant enzyme levels in their bodies to a good extent. The phenolic compounds like rutin, quercetin, etc. has enough contributions in the prevention of peroxidations and scavenger of free radicals. Thus, the inclusion of such green leafy vegetables in the diet is strongly suggested particularly when there is a possibility of pesticide contamination through our diet.

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